

Racial Segregation as Eurocentric Epitome: Black Feminist Study of Toni Morrison's Paradise

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 20, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 17, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Black Feminism, Racial Discrimination, Subjugation, Knowledge, Consciousness</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4546102</p>	<p><i>Morrison's Paradise is a plotless and nonlinear narrative of racial segregation, woman subjugation, terror, and black feminism in a period of struggle for racial and gender consciousness and knowledge in the history of the United States, in the first half of 20th century. A nine all black families who separated from the mainstream society led by white majority, found a new city of Haven and lead the city with the ambitions to build a new community mirrored that of whites. Discontented with their new racial community, they construct a newer one, Ruby, with exclusive schemes to restrict connections with outsiders and other races. Nearby the city of Ruby, there is a convent inhabited by a group of outcast women, homeless and abused, who build an inclusive community in the convent that is open to outsiders from all races. While women in the convent are conscious of their position and aware of feminine rights, the nearby black masculine community of Haven is ignorant and racially oriented, based on the racial system of white dominant class. The black community of the town implemented and internalized the racial system of Eurocentric epitome when they oppress women of the convent and restrict their own wives. The study implies that social change in favor of black feminists requires engagement with new knowledge and revolutionary movements, which its paradigm was presented in in convent women activities.</i></p>

Introduction

Toni Morrison (1931-2019) is an African-American black woman novelist who won the noble prize in literature, awarded for novels that are characterized by visionary force and poetic import which introduced the aspects of American reality in novel. During her literary carrier, she published 11 novels and integrated different themes including race, slavery, violence, and black feminism. The subject of black feminism is highlighted in all novels of Morrison, but it is specifically concerned in *Paradise* (1998), a novel that is based on a general realistic period of time when the constitutional laws "separate but equal" in America caused a wider gap between immigrant blacks and dominant white society (Kunfalvi 7). The segregation laws are known as Jim Crow's laws of racial segregation in late 19th and 20th century in the United States.

In *Paradise*, nine black families separate from the white community to establish a new city named Haven to have their own governance system, a pure black community that excludes non-black races. Their schemes are not applicable and soon they construct another city – Ruby – with severe laws of exclusion and inclusion so that no relationship or contact is allowed with other races. Nearby the city, there is a convent inhabited by a group of outcaste, abused, and homeless women that are eventually massacred by the black male citizens of Ruby. The event in the convent, a symbol of paradise in the novel, can be interpreted in the light of black feminism, gender subjugation and imbalanced white raciest domination and operation.

In "Black Feminist Thought in the Matrix of Domination," Patricia Hill Collins argues that black women's power is imaginable when they are the agents of knowledge, a theoretical idea that can be traced in Morrison's *Paradise*, because women of the convent are independent and the agent of power. Collins believes that, "by portraying African-American women as self-defined, self-reliant individuals confronting race, gender, and class oppression, Afrocentric feminist thought speaks to the importance that oppression, Afrocentric feminist thought speaks to the importance that knowledge plays in empowering oppressed people." In Collins, "consciousness of individuals" and "new knowledge" are basic requirements for paradigm change and social change in case of racial discrimination and gender subjugation. In theory, Collins perceives "Eurocentric masculinist perspectives" are the sources of black women operation and asserts that "power as energy can be fostered by creative acts of resistance." (Collins 222).

Retrospective study of the racial system in America shows blacks as farm workers and slaves who are submissive to their white owners. Even in recent perspectives, racism in America is called colorblind that indicates after 2008 election of Barack Obama as the president of The United States, the prevalent idea was that

the US is mature enough that selected a black president and it implies that racial discrimination is over. However, evidence at the time of Obama's presidency and aftermath indicated that there is "dramatic increase in black incarceration has been attributed to legislative changes in the penal codes" (Bonilla-Silva 45). It reveals that legal procedure is not changed in the US, while it is claimed racial inequality is over. In *Yearning Race, Gender, and Cultural Politics* (1990), Bell Hooks maintains that "black liberation should be defined by the degree to which black people gained equal access to material opportunities and privileges available to whites—jobs, housing, and school" and indicates that though black feminists in 1960s upraised against the racial system, their movement was not revolutionary (15-16). Accordingly, based on what Hooks and Collins indicated, the consciousness, knowledge, and revolutionary movement are the requirement of empowering black women who have been for long the victim of unequal racial system.

In "Mapping the Margins," Kimberlé Crenshaw indicates that black women are victims of "intersecting patterns of racism and sexism" and refers to "their intersectional identity as both women and people of color within discourses that are shaped to respond to one or the other, the interests and experiences of women of color are frequently marginalized within both" (1). In addition, Crenshaw discusses that subordination of black women is due to their passivity and subjugation to dominant power. She claims that "intersectional subordination need not be intentionally produced; in fact, it is frequently the consequence of the imposition of one burden that interacts with preexisting vulnerabilities to create yet another dimension of disempowerment" (4). In general, nearly all feminists consent that resistance, reaction and revolution are the missing points in developing women liberation, especially black women whose condition in terms of Gayatri Spivak is called "double subjugation" (122). In *Double Jeopardy: To Be Black and Female* (1969), Frances Beal explains that being both black and female has been a jeopardy for women, a condition that leads to double marginalization, a condition that women are even dominated by black men (10).

In *Paradise*, Morrison speaks implicitly when she depicts black women in the text. She foregrounds the story of several women who end up in the convent eventually, but she does not mention which of the women in the convent are black. This study sheds light to such buried aspect of *Paradise* to show how black women's voice is chopped in the novel and to what extent they are implied in the novel by ignoring them in the mainstream narrative of the novel. Besides, this study refers to *Paradise* as representative of subjugation's experience for black women and the way resistance, knowledge, and revelation motivate them for demanding their rights that are suppressed in multiple oppressive forms. Though women in the novel are independent of the masculine system, the nearby community does not tolerate them; therefore, the question is that what motivations causes violence and massacre in the convent, and what are the demands of women that are not tolerated by the masculine culture.

Discussion

Morrison's *Paradise* is a narrative of segregation from dominant white society as well as separation from other colors by a black community who seeks racial purity. In the novel, though black men are the agents of changes attributed to racism, black women are subordinate to the masculine system until they find the convent women their own mirror and resist the separatist and segregation laws of their own community. The novel is a plotless narrative of events with women who finally settle in the convent. The setting of the novel is from 1890s to 1976 that represents racial segregation of nine dark black families who intentionally separated from the white community to build up, ironically, a life and community similar to that of whites. In Linda Krumholz, "the irony of paradise is that repetition without a difference maintains itself through rigidity and exclusion and thus destroys the ideal it seeks to preserve; an unchanging paradise inevitably loses its paradisiacal nature" (21).

The decision to part from the dominant white society is a decision as a counterpoint to racial discrimination imposed by whites, but their own reaction is similar, even worse racial idealism. In Haven, the new city, the black community excludes other races from entering the city, but when they failed to establish their plan, they find Ruby suitable for their scheme. However, they try to simulate a community for their own, while in the nearby convent they find a group of women living with inclusive rules; the convent has been previously a place for teaching Indian girls primarily led by a nun called Mother Mary Magna. Women reside in the convent to be independent and away from masculine rules, patriarchal system, the gender discriminations. Collins indicates, "black feminist thought fosters a fundamental paradigmatic shift that rejects additive approaches to oppression" (223). Accordingly, the convent women seek changes in the social system to escape from race, class, and gender oppression.

When Morrison refers to segregation plans, she refers to colorism as a masculine matter, but when she speaks about women, she does not distinguish them by the color as if they are colorless; it implies that Morrison represents women condition suffered by racial segregation and white domination as the primary evidence of discrimination and then as a consequence of subordination and subjugation to the black males in the novel. At the beginning of the novel, Morrison writes, "they shoot the white girl first. With the rest they can take their time" (3). It reveals that when the men of Ruby kill the convent women, they kill both the white girl and other women; it shows that one of the women is white and others are black and Indian. Women in *paradise* are the

victims both of whites and blacks masculine system. Arlinda Banaj considered this idea as “double and triple oppression on black women’s lives and discuss black women’s disadvantaged position in society” (7).

The convent is a paradise to the outcast women who seek their liberation in isolation from both white and black men; meantime, their own society is colorless because their identity is not defined by their color. In Crenshaw’s view intersectionality, to be female and black, “is an analytic sensibility, a way of thinking about identity and its relationship to power” (18). Therefore, power and hegemony of dominant masculine culture is the main agent of intersectionality or marginalization of black women and female subjugation to black community, to black male, is overshadowed by the white dominant culture or Eurocentric epistemology or what Collins calls “Eurocentric masculinist” (222).

The internalization of a system closely the same as that of whites is represented in *Paradise* when the Ruby’s black citizens are proud of their city:

They were proud that none of their women had ever worked in a Whiteman’s kitchen or nursed a white child. Although field labor was harder and carried no status, they believed the rape of women who worked in white kitchens was if not a certainty a distinct possibility—neither of which they could bear to contemplate. (99)

The black men are proud of their scheme of segregation and control over their women; meantime, they are unaware that they have imitated the whites’ racial system. Men of Ruby limited their women to their inclusive city and prevented interaction with outside world. Accordingly, women in the novel are double marginalized: once by the opposition led by Eurocentric thought of white supremacy and black inferiority and the other is black female subjugation to the black and masculine community in which their condition according to Beal as being “both black and female” is a jeopardy for their condition. Beal explains that racism in the United States of America is instrumented to destroy the humanity of the African American people. In this regard, a common misconception is that African American women were less affected by such racist assault than the African American man. However, in reality, it was the African American woman who was the worst affected as she was doubly marginalized (10).

The inclusive convent is, however, a paradise for all women, even if they are retarded or psychic. For instance, Mavis is a Convent woman who suffocated her twin Merle and Pearl in the car because she has not been on her normal mind when she leaves them in the car. And when the journalist asks, “so you left the newborns in the car and went in to buy some chuck steak”, she says “It didn’t. Take long. I couldn’t of been in there more than five minutes, tops.” The Journalist says, “Your babies suffocated, Mrs. Albright. In a hot car with the windows closed. No air. It’s hard to see that happening in five minutes” (*Paradise* 23). This indicates that Mavis is not on her right mind and she is not eligible to be a considerate mother, and both her husband and society marginalized her. Though the convent is open to her, Mavis is primarily victim of patriarchal culture that confused the sexual functions and the motherhood roles, because not all women may be eligible mothers with understanding of complete maternity roles and parenting.

Connie is a girl in the convent who has been raped and kidnapped and finally was brought to the convent by a nun. Seneca is another woman separated from Eddie Turtle, a friend later imprisoned for child abuse. Pallas is a runaway schoolchild from home “trying to escape the wounding memory, she wrecks her car and is then chased by two men into a swampish lake” and cannot speak at first, but gradually speaks in the Convent (Wieland and Beaulieu 265). Gigi or Divine goes to the convent when Magna Mary dies.

In general, all the convent women escaped from masculine aggressive dominant society, because they are either reluctant to undergo male domination or they are shattered mentally and physically in their lives. However, it implies that the society does not perceive the rights for such people and there are no legislative supportive laws or female liberty in the black community of Ruby and the whole United States. Therefore, to such women, the Convent is a promised paradise, but when the citizens of Ruby are inadequate to manage their racial town and flirt women of the convent, they find that the convent is the place that does not let their racial goals fulfill. When the men of Ruby beat their wives, they take refuge in the convent. Accordingly, the convent is perceived an obstacle for establishing and managing the racial black city of Ruby. Hooks indicates that women’s race is prior to their gender in case of discrimination since feminism is a gender-based movement and is concerns equality of genders and it cannot differentiate women’s race. She indicates, “most of us had never been in subordinated position in relation to a white female. Most of us had not been in the workforce” (57).

In *The Identifying Fictions of Toni Morrison*, John Duvall explains, “female subjectivity almost always grows out of violation—child abuse, spousal abuse, molestation, or rape” (142). It indicates that rebellion and revolution as subjectivity element occur when women are oppressed. However, their rebellion should center on their race. In “Separate but equal: racial segregation in The United States,” Lili Kunfalvi declares that by racial laws the rate of violation against women increased and “remind blacks that they were considered so inferior that whites did not want to share public means of transport with them” (11). Accordingly, their lower status in our society with black males is mainly due to white racial laws of segregation than merely the matter of their gender as women. However, “they shoot the white girl first” (*Paradise* 3) indicates that to men of Ruby, racial enmity is more

important, because they think it is the white community that never lets them establish their pure racial community.

Women of Ruby were forbidden from contact with the convent women, but men of Ruby were in touch with them and flirted with the women. Deek and Connie had relationship, K.D and Seneca and Gigi were intimate friends, while the same men deprived their wives from contact with the convent women. According to Pormouzeh “Ruby’s inhabitants try to apply the same scheme performed by whites, try to violate them and keep distance at the same time. Accordingly, the behavior of Ruby’s guys equals that of whites to them is manifestation of systemic violence and racial segregation” (51). Therefore, the black guys implemented the masculine and dominant social system of white community against their own women and outsiders.

When the men kill the women of the convent and after a day bodies disappear, they think bodies are heavenly and confess their own sin:

He and Anna Flood had returned two days after the assault on the Convent women, and it took four days for him to learn what had happened. One, that nine men had gone to talk to and persuade the Convent women to leave or mend their ways; there had been a fight; the women took other shapes and disappeared into thin air. (297)

The story of the convent women and their disappearance indicates that the men of Ruby are not confident about what they have done. They think about their sinful massacre in the convent: “The difficulties churned and entangled everybody: distribution of blame, prayers for understanding and forgiveness, arrogant self-defense, outright lies, and a host of unanswered questions” (*Paradise* 298). It indicates that men of Ruby believe in superstitions and they are simple racist black people who are alienated from their own identity by the white society. This ignorance is so that they kill outsiders due to prejudice and blind imitation of the white dominant society. In fact, they tried “internalization of the Eurocentric episteme” (Pal 49). The condition of black women in Morrison’s novel represent the condition of black women in the United States. African American women are not only physically and economically violated by the white society, but also by the men of their own race. Racist movements in America targeted African Americans in total and it affected both black men and women equally.

In addition to conflict between men and women of Ruby, there was conflict between fathers and their children which reflects the patriarchy and justification of older generation as leaders of family. They perceive that the conflict with younger generation is the intrusion of their symbolic manhood. “We have a problem here. You, me. Everybody. The problem is with the way some of us talk. The grown-ups, of course, should use proper language. But the young people—what they say is more like backtalk than talk” (*Paradise* 85). “You all just don’t want us to talk at all. Any talk is backtalk if you don’t agree with what’s being said” (*Paradise* 85). It reveals that the terms older and grown-up are loaded with meaning components in patriarchal society that does not specify characteristics of the term older appropriately. The patriarchal values of the older people are disrespected by children and women to the same extent and reveals the authority and domination of black males who imitate the episteme of European racial ideology.

The women empowerment though triggered by reference to rebellious cases in Morrison’s novels, in *Paradise* the rebellion and new way of life is started but suppressed by ignorant black male racists. It indicates that women’s movement as Hooks and Collins indicate requires consciousness, knowledge, and revolutionary acts (222). In Collins’s view, in spite of intersectionality condition of black women, it is important to stop and recognize that this way of looking at and living in the world constitutes a new way that is still in its infancy (vii). However, it seems that consciousness and knowledge are requirements of male and female even within different races since Morrison’s *Paradise* reveals that consciousness and knowledge in the convent is not sufficient and effective when the nearby men are ignorant.

The study is in congruous with the idea of Collins who believed that liberation and gaining black female writer requires consciousness about condition of women as those with intersectionality that in Beal is perceived as double marginalization, while Crenshaw refered to it as intersectional identity that means being black and female. As discussed, theorists of black feminism believe that liberation is not possible without being conscious and equipped with knowledge and literacy. In addition, they indicate that these are the primary aids of gaining black female rights, while revolution is totally required.

Conclusion

Morrison’s *Paradise* is the first novel written after winning Noble Prize in 1993. It implies that when writing *Paradise* Morrison was a well-known writer whose playing with different themes in the novel is not occasional, but thoughtful and intentional. She started the novel with the scene of massacre in the convent by killing of several outcast women who settled in the convent with its inclusive aspect that welcomes any woman abused, escaped, or isolated. Morrison narrated the story of liberated women in the symbolic paradise of the convent.

In *Paradise*, Morrison represented the fate of women who gained knowledge to be liberated from the restrictions of masculine society, women who were conscious of their own condition, but constructed a classless community in the convent, a prototypical paradise. The vulnerable point of this society is that their strong

opponents or rivals (black males) are not conscious of their society, with limited knowledge of class-consciousness. Therefore, liberation of women and their knowledge became useless since they are all massacred in the convent by the ignorant men of the nearby city. Therefore, this study indicates that class, gender, and race consciousness of women to gain liberation is not possible without general consciousness of male society. In *Paradise*, the main factor that degrades the black community and moves them to crime and terror is the racial discrimination that primarily targeted the black community so that the segregated blacks follow the same approach against other races that once implemented against their own race, a condition that was referred to as “internalization of Eurocentric epitome” (Pal 49) which degrades black women in the community as double marginalized and renders their identity as intersectional.

In addition, as the novel revealed, knowledge and revolt are the significant aspects of women liberation and independence from the ideological racial segregation schemes and their condition under suppression of black males, which reflects them as double marginalized women. The study implied that different dominating layers are at work in case of black women which their influence may have future consequences in the lives of women and they need to struggle and resist the most powerful ideology that overwhelmed the other dependent sovereign and dominating layers.

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